

Survey form on technical & administrative issues

Project name	DigitAF (101059794)
Work-package	2: Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors
Deliverable	Deliverable 2.1: Survey form on technical & administrative issues.
Date of report	08/06/2024
Authors	Margherita Tranchina, Alice Ripamonti, Alberto Mantino
Contact	alberto.mantino@unipi.it
Approved	Bert Reubens, Marie Gosme (12/06/2024)

Summary

This document, Deliverable D2.1, deals with the design and implementation of a comprehensive survey to gather relevant data for the project's objectives and activities. While originally the deliverable was intended to focus on a specific survey on “technical & administrative issues”, it was agreed quite early in the project’s process that an integration of the various survey plans in several of the project’s tasks, would increase efficiency, optimize stakeholders’ efforts and result in a more comprehensive and high-quality outcome. The survey is intended to capture various stakeholder perspectives and will be instrumental in informing subsequent phases of the project.

The first section of this deliverable provides background information on the project's scope, objectives, and the specific needs that the survey aims to address. It emphasizes the importance of gathering accurate and diverse stakeholder inputs to ensure the project's success. The second section reiterates the significance of the survey within the broader framework of the project. It highlights the methodological approach adopted for the survey design, including the rationale behind the selection of specific questions and the anticipated impact of the collected data.

The survey questions are designed to capture detailed insights from participants. They cover a range of topics pertinent to the project's objectives, including demographic information, stakeholder opinions, and specific feedback related to project activities.

The survey data will be utilized to:

1. **Guide Decision-Making:** The insights gained from the survey will guide key decisions throughout the project lifecycle.
2. **Identify Stakeholder Needs:** Understanding stakeholder perspectives will help tailor project activities to meet their needs effectively.
3. **Measure Impact:** The survey will serve as a baseline to measure the impact of project interventions over time.
4. **Enhance Engagement:** Regular feedback from stakeholders will foster ongoing engagement and collaboration.

Deliverable D2.1 outlines a critical component of our project, detailing the design and intended use of a comprehensive survey. The collected data will play a pivotal role in guiding project activities and achieving the desired outcomes.

Table of contents:

1	The DigitAF project	3
2	Task and deliverable description	3
3	Background literature and survey development/ considerations.....	4
4	Survey structure of technical and administrative issues	7
5	Complementary and coordination efforts	11
6	Acknowledgements.....	11
7	References	12
8	Annex I – Entire DIGITAF Survey (including the technical and administrative issues subsections)	13

1 The DigitAF project

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Participatory research approach is key to engage with actors involved in the development of agroforestry and to unlock synergies among stakeholders to facilitate the implementation of innovations. In this preliminary action of the project, our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs and expectation, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are targeted by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report introduces and presents the work conducted to develop the multi-stakeholder survey aimed at discovering technical and administrative issues faced by these stakeholder groups.

2 Task and deliverable description

The deliverable is found in the context of the DigitAF Work Package (WP) 2, which deals with optimising agroforestry design and management and tools for practitioners and farm advisors. More specifically, it is in the context of task 2.1: dealing with technical, administrative and financial aspects of installing and managing agroforestry.

Specifically, Deliverable 2.1 consists of a multi-actor survey form on technical & administrative challenges, co-developed with the six Living Labs and WP4 leaders. The results of the survey will be used as an input for Deliverable 2.2. (Roadmap on tools for technical & administrative issues – M36).

The questionnaire was constructed in English to facilitate inputs from different contributors: translation/adaptation work was going to follow. One goal at project level was for the questionnaire to be integrated with other activities and surveys of the DigitAF project, as explained in Section 5 (Coordination efforts).

3 Background literature and survey development/ considerations

The 2.1 questionnaire was developed as structured and self-administered, although a possibility could be to administer the questionnaire through videocalls or phone calls to optimize data collection and guide the intended user through the questions. Still, all questionnaires should be administered following the same protocol and assuring the absence of bias or encouragement towards certain responses.

The goal was to develop a questionnaire that would not be too long or complex, limiting the questions to those necessary to provide the data for analysis. Questions were formulated in a clear, non-biased way, avoiding merging two concepts in one single question.

The main goal of this survey was to discover the perception of stakeholders involved in agroforestry (farmers, advisors, researchers, policymakers, etc.) regarding the (technical and administrative) obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices in Europe, to eventually focus further project efforts in task 2.1 on the most problematic points, through pilot-testing novel techniques, providing better (digital) tools to deal with these challenges, and sharing knowledge.

3.1 Previous research investigating challenges to the implementation of agroforestry in Europe:

Previous research (Rolo et al. 2020) was examined and studied as inspiration and guidance literature. However, albeit informative, it was found to focus and gather data on quite broad categories. The goal of this survey, although by no means exhaustive, was to pave the way towards a more in-depth analysis, crucial to provide more accurate and concrete solutions and digital tools to farmers and other stakeholders involved in the agroforestry value chain.

Research carried out in the context of the AGFORWARD project, consisting of stakeholder meetings in 11 EU Countries (Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom), gathered the perception of 344 participants, that were asked to rank the benefits and drawbacks of utilizing agroforestry practices in their area. The main negative

aspects that emerged were the following: increased labour, complexity of work, management costs and administrative burden (García de Jalón et al,2018). However, the proposed categories are quite broad and fail to showcase which aspect of technical management specifically, for instance, results into increased workload (harvesting actions, pest control, etc.)

Another resource analyzing the perception of stakeholders in Italy in the context of the AGFORWARD project highlighted that bureaucratic complexity of CAP discourages farmers from applying for grants: farmers perceived that trees in fields could be obstacles because they caused the reduction of CAP payments. Nevertheless, the quantitative information originating from AGFORWARD workshops was not able to reflect this aspect nor break down the category of “administrative burden” and “subsidy eligibility” (Camilli et al., 2018).

These results are in line with past research. Interviews carried between 2003 and 2004 showed that farmers in Mediterranean areas perceived the main drawbacks of silvoarable systems to be intercrop yield decline , whereas farmers in Northern Europe tended to highlight the general complexity of work and difficulties with mechanization (Graves et al, 2009).-Results from research carried out in the context of the SAFE (20012-2005) project show that the main concern of farmers in Spain, France, England, Italy, Greece, Germany and the Netherlands in relations to silvoarable systems is the yield and quality of the crop, followed by work complexity, mechanization and project feasibility (Liagre et al., 2005).

The objective of this survey is on the one hand to try and further break down categories of perceived issues, and secondly to verify if the results from different European regions nowadays either confirm or show differences from the researched carried on 10 or 20 years ago, both in general trends and in differences across pedo-climatic regions.

3.2 Drafting of the first survey version and consulted literature on methodological issues

A first version was drafted, initially only directed towards farmers and advisors, making use of conditional logics as the main feature of Google Forms to diversify survey question based on previous answers.

Figure 1 Visual representation of the initial version of the survey

The initial survey was then presented to the broader working group in the DigitAF project and modified through shortening, fine-tuning and clarifying actions.

The literature was also consulted regarding pre-testing actions in order to properly evaluate and test survey questions (Presser et al. 2004).

To gain knowledge regarding survey design in agriculture contexts, various sources were consulted, providing insights on case studies and survey development, administering and data analysis (Nguyen-Thi-Lan et al. 2021). Various documents were consulted in order to gather information regarding the obstacles to the application of agroforestry in various contexts, and therefore inspiration for constructing survey questions and developing insightful categories for users to choose amongst. These include but are not limited to:

- Decision makers guide for policymakers (Buttoud 2013) for AF promotion
- Methodological papers regarding FAO agricultural surveys (Fonteneau 2016) and World Bank documentations on agricultural survey design (Dillon et al. 2021) .
- Scientific papers collecting insight on response trends (Pennings et al., 2002), farmers perceptions (Elbers et al. 2010; Case et al. 2017; Hannus 2020), participatory methodologies and semi structure interviews (Chen et al. 2013).
- Documents regarding policy related issues and Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plans (Chesnoiu 2021), official EC resources (European Commission 2017, 2019) and websites as well as resources from the European Agroforestry Federation.

This resulted in an iterative survey design process, paired with input implementation from the survey working group, ultimately resulting in the survey presented in section 8.

The survey data will play a critical role in the project by guiding decision-making, identifying stakeholder needs, measuring impact and enhancing engagement. By analysing the insights gained from the survey, the project team can make evidence-based decisions throughout the project lifecycle, ensuring strategic planning and implementation. Understanding stakeholder perspectives will enable the tailoring of project activities to meet their needs more effectively, thereby increasing relevance and acceptance. The survey will also serve as a baseline for measuring the impact of interventions over time, allowing the team to track progress, evaluate outcomes, and provide transparent reports to stakeholders. Additionally, regular feedback through the survey will foster ongoing engagement and collaboration, maintaining an open line of communication that adapts to changing needs and builds a sense of community and shared purpose among stakeholders. This integrated approach underscores the project's commitment to data-driven planning and stakeholder-centred execution.

4 Survey structure of technical and administrative issues

Question	Answer type/options
I confirm that I have read and understand the information provided on this form and give my consent to taking part in this research.	Accept; Decline
Please indicate if this response is part of the testing process or if it's the actual response you wish to give to the questions.	"Test" answer, Actual answer
Please enter your personal code below. This was previously assigned to you by DigitAF staff	Short answer
1.1 (1.1) Please select your age :	18-35 years old, 36-50 years old, 51-65 years old, 66+, Prefer not to say,
1.2 (1.2) What is your gender ?	Male, Female, Other, Prefer not to say
1.3 In which country do you carry out your business or activities? (farming, farm advising, research, etc.)	Country name
1.4 (1.3) What is the highest level of education you have completed?	No formal education, Secondary school (up to 16 y-old), High school (up to 18 y-old), Bachelor's degree or equivalent, Master's degree or equivalent, Doctoral or above, Prefer not to say,
1.5 (1.4) What type of stakeholder are you?	Farmer or landowner, Farm advisor, Policymaker, Stakeholder in the value chain, Researcher,
1.6 F (1.7.F) Please indicate the size of your farm in ha*	Short answer
1.7.F (1.8.F) What is your farm type ? (you can select more than one option)*	Arable, Horticulture (vegetables), Horticulture tree crops (e.g. Olive, apples, vine), Mixed (Livestock + Crops), Livestock (Pigs), Livestock (Poultry), Livestock (Beef and sheep), Livestock (Dairy), Agroforestry, Forestry, Agri-tourism and education, Organic,
1.6.A (1.7.A) What types of farm do you advise? (you can select more than one option)**	Arable, Horticulture (vegetables), Horticulture tree crops (e.g. Olive, apples, vine), Mixed (Livestock + Crops), Livestock (Pigs), Livestock (Poultry), Livestock (Beef and sheep), Livestock (Dairy), Agroforestry, Forestry, Agri-tourism and education, Organic,
1.5b Do you also have a secondary stakeholder role ? (ex. you're a farmer but you're also a researcher)	yes, Farmer or landowner, yes, Farm advisor, yes, Policymaker, yes, Stakeholder in the value chain, yes, Researcher, No, I do not have a secondary stakeholder role,

3.1 (6.1) How do you rate your knowledge of agroforestry systems?	5
3.2 (6.3) Which of the following practices do you associate with agroforestry?	Biodynamic orchard, Wood pasture, Alley cropping, Hedges, Regenerative farming, Grazed orchard and woodland, Shelterbelts and windbreaks, Kitchen gardens, Riparian buffer strips, Dehesa and montado, Silvopastoral system, Silvoarable system, Farm woodlands, Short-rotation coppice, Increasing tree cover on farm, Forest gardening, None of the previous,
Would you like to respond to some questions related to the obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? (This will take 4-5 minutes) All stakeholders can fill in this section	Yes, No
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Increased complexity of AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Level of knowledge regarding the management of trees on farmland]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Availability of resources regarding the management of AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Availability of species adequate to be grown in AF systems (cereals, fodder crops)]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Interaction with livestock]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Effect on the yields of the main crop]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Changes in agro-mechanical operations]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Presence	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant

of a network of knowledge regarding technical issues related to AF systems]	
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Harvesting fruits/ nuts from the trees]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Pruning of the trees]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Technical knowledge of agricultural workers (employees)]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Water provision of young trees]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.16 (6.5) Please indicate any other TECHNICAL or AGRONOMIC obstacle to the application of agroforestry you perceive and rate it from 0-5	Short answer
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Management of weeds]	A-Less complicated; B- More complicated;C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Management of pests/ diseases]	A-Less complicated; B- More complicated;C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Crop harvesting operations]	A-Less complicated; B- More complicated;C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Reduction in pesticide use]	A-Less complicated; B- More complicated;C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Soil tillage practices]	A-Less complicated; B- More complicated;C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Fertilization plan]	A-Less complicated; B- More complicated;C- Equally complicated

4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Crop species selection]	A-Less complicated; B- More complicated;C- Equally complicated
4.16.b What kind of information/tools/support would you like to see provided regarding these aspects?	Short answer
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Access to financing]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Necessity of large investments to set up AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Management cost of agroforestry systems]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Diminished income related to the primary crops]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Insufficient future revenue to manage the AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.18 (6.7) Please indicate any other ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry you perceive and rate them from 0-5	Short answer
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Administrative burden when implementing AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to accountancy]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to land ownership]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to permits for planting trees]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant

agroforestry practices: [Issues related to permits for removing trees]	
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to food safety]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to permits for agroforestry-related infrastructure]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Entity of support of Common Agricultural Policy measures]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Fear that an increased number of trees/ ha would result in losing CAP support (basic payment related to agricultural land)]	0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant
4.20 (6.9) Please indicate any other ADMINISTRATIVE obstacle to the application of agroforestry you perceive and rate them from 0-5	Short answer

5 Complementary and coordination efforts

In order to optimize efforts and resource uses throughout the DigitAF project, at project level the choice was made to examine survey objectives and timelines throughout the project. Subsequently, synergies were found, and the decision was taken to create one single multi-stakeholder survey, therefore reducing time and burdens on future respondents that would have otherwise had to fill in many surveys and basic information questions (1.1-1.6 and 3.1-3.2) multiple times.

Coordination efforts by UNIFI consisted in receiving input from different work packages, converting and adapting questions into Google Form, language and spelling revisions, merging/removing/adding questions and sections as well as implementing improvements and changes both discussed during meetings and received via emails. In fact, the survey presented in Section 4 is a section of the larger, integrated survey attached to this document as Annex I.

6 Acknowledgements

The DigitAF project (Grant Agreement N° 101059794) is co-funded by the European Commission, European Research Agency, within the Horizon Europe programme, Cluster 6: “Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment”. The views and opinions expressed in this report are purely those of the writers and may not in any circumstances be regarded as stating an official position of the European Commission.

7 References

- Buttoud G (2013) Advancing agroforestry on the policy agenda – a guide for decision-makers
- Camilli F, Pisanelli A, Seddaiu G, et al (2018) How local stakeholders perceive agroforestry systems: an Italian perspective. *Agrofor Syst* 92:849–862. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0127-0>
- Case SDC, Oelofse M, Hou Y, et al (2017) Farmer perceptions and use of organic waste products as fertilisers – A survey study of potential benefits and barriers. *Agric Syst* 151:84–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agry.2016.11.012>
- Chen Q, Cai Y, Liu F, et al (2013) Farmers' perception to farmland conversion: A questionnaire survey in Xining City, Qinghai Province, China. *Chinese Geogr Sci* 23:634–646. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11769-013-0624-7>
- Chesnoiu IA (2021) Perception of Farmers on EC Recommendations for Romania's CAP Strategic Plan. 862–870. <https://doi.org/10.24818/basiq/2021/07/108>
- Dillon A, Carletto G, Gourlay S, et al (2021) Agricultural Survey Design. Lessons from the LSMS-ISA and Beyond. 148
- Elbers ARW, de Koeijer AA, Scolamacchia F, van Rijn PA (2010) Questionnaire survey about the motives of commercial livestock farmers and hobby holders to vaccinate their animals against Bluetongue virus serotype 8 in 2008-2009 in the Netherlands. *Vaccine* 28:2473–2481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2010.01.047>
- European Commission (2017) Technical Handbook on the Monitoring and Evaluation Framework of the Common Agricultural Policy 2014 – 2020. 85
- European Commission (2019) Analysis of administrative burden arising from the CAP
- Fonteneau F (2016) THE AGRICULTURAL INTEGRATED SURVEY (AGRIS): RATIONALE , METHODOLOGY , IMPLEMENTATION. 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1481/icasVII.2016.f34d>
- García de Jalón S, Burgess PJ, Graves A, et al (2018) How is agroforestry perceived in Europe? An assessment of positive and negative aspects by stakeholders. *Agrofor Syst* 92:829–848. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0116-3>
- Graves AR, Burgess PJ, Liagre F, Pisanelli A, Paris P, Moreno G, Bellido M, Mayus M, Postma M, Schindler B, Mantzanas K, Papanastasis VP, Dupraz C (2009) Farmer perceptions of silvoarable systems in seven European countries. In: Rigueiro-Rodríguez A, McAdam J, Mosquera-Losada MR (eds) *Agroforestry in Europe. Curr Status Futur Prospects*, Springer, p 450
- Hannus V (2020) Data on farmers' perception and acceptance of sustainability standards. *Data Br* 32:106250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2020.106250>
- Liagre F, Pisanelli A, Moreno G, Bellido M, Mayus M, Postma M, Schindler B, Graves A, Mantzanas K, Dupraz C (2005) Survey of farmers' reaction to modern silvoarable systems. Deliverable 2.3 of the Silvoarable Agroforestry For Europe (SAFE) project, European Research contract QLK5-CT-2001-00560. Available at: <http://www1.montpellier.inra.fr/safe/english/results/final-report/Deliverable%202.3.pdf>
- Nguyen-Thi-Lan H, Fahad S, Nguyen-Anh T, et al (2021) Assessment of farm households' perception, beliefs and attitude toward climatic risks: A case study of rural Vietnam. *PLoS One* 16:1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0258598>
- Pennings, J.M.E., Irwin, S.H. and Good, D.L. (2002), *Surveying Farmers: A Case Study. Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 24: 266-277. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9353.00096>
- Presser S, Couper MP, Lessler JT, et al (2004) Methods for testing and evaluating survey questions. *Public Opin Q* 68:109–130. <https://doi.org/10.1093/poq/nfh008>
- Rolo V, Hartel T, Aviron S, et al (2020) Challenges and innovations for improving the sustainability of European agroforestry systems of high nature and cultural value: stakeholder perspectives. *Sustain Sci* 15:1301–1315. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00826-6>

8 Annex I – Entire DIGITAF Survey (including the technical and administrative issues subsections)

Questions	Answers (options are separated with a “, ”)
I confirm that I have read and understand the information provided on this form and give my consent to taking part in this research.	Accept, Decline
Please indicate if this response is part of the testing process or if it's the actual response you wish to give to the questions.	"Test" answer, Actual answer
Please enter your personal code below. This was previously assigned to you by DigitAF staff	personal code
1.1 (1.1) Please select your age:	18-35 years old, 36-50 years old, 51-65 years old, 66+, Prefer not to say,
1.2 (1.2) What is your gender?	Male, female, other, prefer not to say
1.3 In which country do you carry out your business or activities? (farming, farm advising, research, etc.)	open answer
1.4 (1.3) What is the highest level of education you have completed?	No formal education, Secondary school (up to 16 y-old), High school (up to 18 y-old), Bachelor's degree or equivalent, Master's degree or equivalent, Doctoral or above, Prefer not to say,
1.5 (1.4) What type of stakeholder are you?	Farmer or landowner, Farm advisor, Policymaker, Stakeholder in the value chain, Researcher,
1.6 F (1.7.F) Please indicate the size of your farm in ha	open answer
1.7.F (1.8.F) What is your farm type? (you can select more than one option)	Arable, Horticulture (vegetables), Horticulture tree crops (e.g. Olive, apples, vine), Mixed (Livestock + Crops), Livestock (Pigs), Livestock (Poultry), Livestock (Beef and sheep), Livestock (Dairy), Agroforestry, Forestry, Agri-tourism and education, Organic,
1.6.A (1.7.A) What types of farm do you advise? (you can select more than one option)	Arable, Horticulture (vegetables), Horticulture tree crops (e.g. Olive, apples, vine), Mixed (Livestock + Crops), Livestock (Pigs), Livestock (Poultry), Livestock (Beef and sheep), Livestock (Dairy), Agroforestry, Forestry, Agri-tourism and education, Organic,
1.5b Do you also have a secondary stakeholder role? (ex. you're a farmer but you're also a researcher)	yes, Farmer or landowner, yes, Farm advisor, yes, Policymaker, yes, Stakeholder in the value chain, yes, Researcher, No, I do not have a secondary stakeholder role
2.1 (2.1) In your business, do you use digital tools for the following	Decision support, Research, Training,

<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Climate and weather data]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Geographical data (e.g. field layout)]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Soil and nutrients (e.h. fertilization plans)]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Economy / Market (e.g. prices)]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Policy (e.g. Subsidies)]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Animal nutrition and welfare]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Biodiversity (e.g. wild species)]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Energy and GHGs emissions (CO2 eq)]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p> <p>2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Tree/ crop species selection]</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>
<p>Digital tools involve the use of both data and models</p>	<p>not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable</p>

2.2 (2.3) What data have you used or are you currently using? [Other]	
2.2a (2.3a) If you ticked "Others" - please describe	open answer
Digital tools involve the use of both data and models	not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable
2.3 (2.4) In what thematic area have you used or are you currently using digital models? [Technical (agronomic and managerial aspects)]	
Digital tools involve the use of both data and models	not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable
2.3 (2.4) In what thematic area have you used or are you currently using digital models? [Economy (financial. labor assessments)]	
Digital tools involve the use of both data and models	not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable
2.3 (2.4) In what thematic area have you used or are you currently using digital models? [Policy (Subsidies)]	
Digital tools involve the use of both data and models	not used before, used before, currently using, not applicable
2.3 (2.4) In what thematic area have you used or are you currently using digital models? [Others (please elaborate in the next question)]	
2.3a (2.4a) Are there digital models or tools that are particularly useful to your business? Can you please provide their names?	open answer
2.4 (2.5) In your opinion, what makes a good digital tool?	open answer
3.1 (6.1) How do you rate your knowledge of agroforestry systems?	1-5 scale
3.2 (6.3) Which of the following practices do you associate with agroforestry?	Biodynamic orchard, Wood pasture, Alley cropping, Hedges, Regenerative farming, Grazed orchard and woodland, Shelterbelts and windbreaks, Kitchen gardens, Riparian buffer strips, Dehesa and montado, Silvopastoral system, Silvoarable system, Farm woodlands, Short-rotation coppice, Increasing tree cover on farm, Forest gardening, None of the previous,
3.3 (4.4) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the management of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes [Tree selection in agroforestry]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful

3.3 (4.4) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the management of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes [System design for agroforestry]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.3 (4.4) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the management of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes [Tree performance in agroforestry]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.3 (4.4) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the management of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes [Crop performance in agroforestry]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.3 (4.4) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the management of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes [Animal performance in agroforestry]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.3 (4.4) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the management of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes [Management guidance in agroforestry]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.4 (4.5) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the economic aspects of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes? [Financial performance of agroforestry]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.4 (4.5) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the economic aspects of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes? [Implication of agroforestry for CAP or government payments]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.4 (4.5) According to your perception, would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the economic aspects of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes? [Identify suppliers or buyers]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.5 (4.6) Would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the environmental aspects of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes? [Biodiversity performance of agroforestry]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful
3.5 (4.6) Would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the environmental aspects of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes? [Carbon neutrality of agroforestry (Net zero greenhouse performance)]	Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful

<p>3.5 (4.6) Would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the environmental aspects of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes? [Soil health performance of agroforestry]</p>	<p>Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful</p>
<p>3.5 (4.6) Would a new or enhanced digital tool or model regarding the environmental aspects of agroforestry systems be useful for the following purposes? [Other environmental performance of agroforestry]</p>	<p>Not of interest, Could be useful, Could be very useful</p>
<p>3.6 (2.8b) In general, what platform would be most effective for using digital tools or models for agroforestry?</p>	<p>Smartphone, Laptop and desktop, Tablet,</p>
<p>Would you like to respond to some policy-related questions? (This section will take 3-4 minutes)</p> <p>If you are not a farmer or policymaker, please select "no" to move forward in the survey completion</p>	<p>Yes and I am a farmer, Yes and I am a policymaker, No, because I am not interested, No, because I am not a farmer nor a policymaker</p>
<p>4.1F (5.1F [1.1.a]) Were you interested in tree-planting schemes in Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2014-2022?</p>	<p>Yes, No, Not sure: I am not familiar with this concept,</p>
<p>4.2.F (5.2F [1.1.b]) Are you interested in the new agroforestry / carbon farming in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2028?</p>	<p>Yes, No, Not sure: I am not familiar with this concept,</p>
<p>4.3.F (5.3F [1.2.a]) From the list below, please select the EU land monitoring indicators of your interest.</p>	<p>C.05 - Corine Land Cover Classes for your farm and municipality - and how these have changed?, C.18 - Irrigable land for farm and province (from the Farm Structure Survey - FSS), C.19 - Areas in Natura 2000 etc. (e.g. N sensitive areas) for farm and province (NUTS3), C.20 Areas facing natural and other specific constraints for province (reported by Member States), C.21 Area of Landscape Features in your farm and municipality (NUTS4) - calculated from the LPIS, C.22 Crop diversity index in your farm and province (NUTS3) - areas with 1,2,3 crops from FSS, C.22 Livestock units in your farm and province (NUTS3) from FSS, C.23 Livestock density in your farm and province (NUTS3) from FSS, C.24 Area under organic farming in farm and province (NUTS3) from FSS, C.36 Farmland Bird Index (from nearest available survey), C.38 Water use in Agriculture (from soil survey (WISE) data for farm and province), C. 39 Water quality farm and province (gross N and P balance and nitrates in groundwater), C. 40 Soil organic carbon in agricultural land (farm, municipality and province), C.41 Soil erosion by water (Revised Universal Soil Loss</p>

	Equation - RUSLE - for farm and province), C.42 Sustainable production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry (farm and province), C.43 Energy use in agriculture and forestry (farm and province), C.44 Greenhouse gas emissions and sequestration in agriculture and forestry (farm and province), C.45 Agricultural Sector resilience progress indicator (farm and province), C.46 Direct agricultural loss attributed to disasters (farm and province), C.47 Ammonia emissions from agriculture (farm and province),
4.4.F (5.4 F [1.3.a]) Have you identified tree landscape features (hedges, isolated trees, lines of trees, groups of trees) on your farm in accordance with the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2028?	Yes, No, Not sure: I am not familiar with this concept,
4.5.F (5.5F [1.3.b]) Do you have areas of official "forest" on your land?	Yes, No, I'm not sure if the Government classes my small copses as "forest" or not.,
4.6.F (5.6F [1.3.c]) Will you be planting more tree landscape features (hedges, isolated trees, lines of trees, groups of trees) on your land?	Yes, No, Perhaps - depends on the details,
4.7.F (5.7F [1.3.d]) Will you be implementing new agroforestry or landscape features on your land?	Yes, No, Perhaps - depends on the details,
4.8.F (5.8F [1.4.a]) Will you apply for an voluntary carbon farming scheme when it is launched in your country (More info)?	Yes, No, Perhaps - depends on the details,
4.9.F (5.9F [1.4.b]) If available, will you apply for an agroforestry scheme? (to aid with the design, establishment or management of agroforestry on your farm)	Yes, No, Perhaps - depends on the details,
4.10.F (5.10F [1.4.c]) Will you apply for a Pillar I scheme "ecoscheme" involving trees?	Yes, No, Perhaps - depends on the details,
4.11.F (5.11F [1.5.a]) Are you willing to share your Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) data confidentially with project staff?	Yes, No, Maybe - need to discuss further,
4.12.F (5.12F [1.5.b]) Are you happy with the choice of landscape features made by your country (see Table 1 in this link)?	Yes, No, Not sure - I need to check the details,
4.13.F (5.13F [1.5.c]) In your opinion, how could the data collected by the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) in your country be improved?	open answer
4.1.P (5.1P [1.1.a]) In your opinion, what were the problems/advantages of tree-planting schemes under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2014-2022?	open answer
4.2.P (5.2P [1.1.b]) Does the new agroforestry / carbon farming in CAP 2023-2028 meet the needs of your region/country?	open answer

4.3.P (5.3P [1.2.a]) Choose from this list of indicators (link) those which interest you and write them down here:	open answer
4.4.P (5.4P [1.3.a]) Under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2028, have landscape features been fully identified in your region?	open answer
4.5.P (5.5P [1.3.b]) Does your Land Parcel Identification System (IACS/LPIS) identify "official forest"?	open answer
4.6.P (5.6P [1.3.c]) Are you interested in how landscape features are recorded in other Member States?	open answer
4.7.P (5.7P [1.3.d]) Is it clear which Landscape Features are flagged for "retention" and which count towards the GAEC8 threshold?	open answer
4.8.P (5.8P [1.3.e]) Are you aware of whether your Member State includes 'Trees outside Forests' in their land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF) returns?	open answer
4.9.P (5.9P [1.4.a]) Is your region implementing tree planting/carbon farming in Pillar I?	open answer
4.10.P (5.10P [1.4.b]) is your region implementing tree planting/carbon farming in Pillar II?	open answer
4.11.P (5.11P [1.4.c]) What is your view on the proposed EU Framework on Carbon Removals (link)?	open answer
4.12.P (5.12P [1.5.a]) What use do you make of the existing LPIS/IACS data?	open answer
4.13.P (5.13P [1.5.b]) How could use of LPIS/IACS data be improved?	open answer
4.14.P (5.14P [1.5.c]) Have you heard of the FaST system? How will it be used in your country?	open answer
Would you like to respond to some questions related to the obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? (This will take 4-5 minutes)	Yes, No
All stakeholders can fill in this section	
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Increased complexity of AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Level of knowledge regarding the management of trees on farmland]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant

4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Availability of resources regarding the management of AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Availability of species adequate to be grown in AF systems (cereals, fodder crops)]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Interaction with livestock]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Effect on the yields of the main crop]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Changes in agro-mechanical operations]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Presence of a network of knowledge regarding technical issues related to AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Harvesting fruits/ nuts from the trees]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Pruning of the trees]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Technical knowledge of agricultural workers (employees)]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.15 (6.4) Please rate how you perceive the following potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices [Water provision of young trees]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.16 (6.5) Please indicate any other TECHNICAL or AGRONOMIC obstacle to the application of agroforestry you perceive and rate it from 0-5	open answer
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Management of weeds]	A-Less complicated, B- More complicated, C- Equally complicated

4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Management of pests/ diseases]	A-Less complicated, B- More complicated, C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Crop harvesting operations]	A-Less complicated, B- More complicated, C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Reduction in pesticide use]	A-Less complicated, B- More complicated, C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Soil tillage practices]	A-Less complicated, B- More complicated, C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Fertilization plan]	A-Less complicated, B- More complicated, C- Equally complicated
4.16a Do you think that the following aspects of agricultural management become more/less complicated when implementing agroforestry systems? [Crop species selection]	A-Less complicated, B- More complicated, C- Equally complicated
4.16.b What kind of information/tools/support would you like to see provided regarding these aspects?	open answer
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Access to financing]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Necessity of large investments to set up AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Management cost of agroforestry systems]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Diminished income related to the primary crops]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant

4.17 (6.6) Please rate, how do you perceive the following potential ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices? [Insufficient future revenue to manage the AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X - Not relevant
4.18 (6.7) Please indicate any other ECONOMIC obstacles to the application of agroforestry you perceive and rate them from 0-5	open answer
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Administrative burden when implementing AF systems]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to accountancy]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to land ownership]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to permits for planting trees]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to permits for removing trees]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to food safety]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Issues related to permits for agroforestry-related infrastructure]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Entity of support of Common Agricultural Policy measures]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.19 (6.8) Please rate the following potential ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices: [Fear that an increased number of trees/ ha would result in losing CAP support (basic payment related to agricultural land)]	0- Not problematic at all, 1- Slightly problematic, 2- Problematic, 3- Very problematic, 4- Extremely problematic, X- Not relevant
4.20 (6.9) Please indicate any other ADMINISTRATIVE obstacle to the application of agroforestry you perceive and rate them from 0-5	open answer

<p>Would you like to respond to some further questions about tree soil and animal interactions regarding agroforestry systems and digital models and tools?</p> <p>(This will take 7-9 minutes)</p>	Yes, No
<p>4.21 (7.1) Do you think a decision support digital model or tool on agroforestry system design would be useful for yourself?</p> <p>(ex. species selection, architecture of the system, etc.)</p>	Linear scale 1-5
4.21a (7.1a) Briefly explain why	open answer
4.22 (7.2) Do you know of any existing digital models or tools on agroforestry system design?	Yes, No,
4.22a (7.2a) If you answered yes - please mention which one(s)	open answer
4.23 (7.3) What parameters should be further incorporated in digital models or tools for the design of agroforestry systems?	soil conditions, hydrology, topography, tree and crop species choice, adaptability to mechanisation / machinery use, water management, biodiversity optimisation, carbon storage optimisation, management after planting,
4.24 (7.4) Which other aspects can be improved in existing digital models or tools for the design of agroforestry systems?	user friendliness, visualisation, scale, language,
4.25 (7.5) Would a digital model or tool on tree species or variety selection be useful to support decision making in agroforestry?	Linear scale 1-5
4.25a (7.5a) Briefly explain why	open answer
4.26 (7.6) Do you know of any existing digital models or tools on tree species or variety choice ?	Yes, No
4.26a (7.6a) If you answered yes - please mention which one(s)	open answer
4.27 (7.7) What parameters should be further incorporated in existing digital models or tools for the selection of tree species or variety in agroforestry systems?'	soil requirements, hydrology, climate requirements, combination options with other species, growth speed or productivity, marketing options, ecological value, drought tolerance, shade tolerance, pest or disease resistance,
4.28 (7.8) Which other aspects can be improved in existing digital models or tools for the selection of tree species or variety in agroforestry systems?	user friendliness, visualisation, scale, language,
4.29 (7.9) Would a digital model or tool on predicting crop and/or tree performance be useful to support decision making in agroforestry?	Linear scale 1-5
4.29a (7.9a) Briefly explain why	open answer
4.30 (7.10) Do you know of any existing digital models or tools on crop or tree performance?	Yes, No,

4.30a (7.10a) If you answered yes - please mention which one(s)	open answer
4.31 (7.11) What parameters should be further incorporated in existing digital models or tools to estimate crop and tree performance in agroforestry?	water availability, nutrient availability, light availability, soil carbon content, climate change scenario's, impact of pests or diseases,
4.32 (7.12) Which other aspects can be improved in existing digital models or tools to estimate crop and tree performance in agroforestry systems?	user friendliness, visualisation, scale, language,
4.33 (7.13) Would a digital model or tool on tree management be useful to support decision making in agroforestry?'	Linear scale 1-5
4.33a (7.13a) Briefly explain why	open answer
4.34 (7.14) Do you know of any existing tools on tree management in agroforestry?	Yes, No
4.34a (7.14a) If you answered yes - please mention which one(s)	open answer
4.35 (7.15) What parameters should be further incorporated in existing digital models or tools for tree management in agroforestry?	pruning requirements, health check, water provision, protection against pests or diseases, protection against animals, avoiding competition, productivity optimisation,
4.36 (7.16) Which other aspects can be improved in existing digital models or tools for tree management in agroforestry systems?	user friendliness, visualisation, scale, language,
4.37 (7.17) Would a digital model or tool on animal performance be useful to support decision making in agroforestry?	Linear scale 1-5
4.37a (7.17a) Briefly explain why	open answer
4.38 (7.18) Do you know of any existing digital models or tools on animal performance in agroforestry?	Yes, No,
4.38a (7.18a) If you answered yes - please mention which one(s)	open answer
4.39 (7.19) What parameters should be further incorporated in existing digital models or tools for animal performance in agroforestry?	protection against wind, protection against sunlight, (tree) fodder provision, tree damage, natural behaviour, animal health, animal productivity, risks of intoxication,
4.40 (7.20) Which other aspects can be improved in existing digital models or tools for animal performance in agroforestry systems?	user friendliness, visualisation, scale, language,
4.41 (7.21) If there is any other topic related to agroforestry system design, management or evaluation on which you believe support tools would be helpful - please describe	open answer
Would you like to respond to some further questions about biodiversity?	Yes, No
(This will take 4-5 minutes)	
4.42 (8.1) How important do you consider biodiversity in agro-ecosystems?	Not at all important, Somewhat important, Neutral, Important, Very important

<p>4.43 (8.2) Do you know any biodiversity assessment digital models or tools? (e.g. software to quantify biodiversity)</p>	<p>Yes, No</p>
<p>4.44 (8.3) If yes, which ones?</p> <p>(Add as many answers as you desire on separate lines)</p>	<p>open answer</p>
<p>4.45 (8.4) Do you think a digital model or tool predicting biodiversity in agroforestry systems would be useful?</p> <p>This tool could be used to enter the specifications of a field/farm and would give as an output a proxy for biodiversity under these circumstances.</p>	<p>Not at all important, Somewhat important, Neutral, Important, Very important</p>
<p>4.46 (8.5) Briefly explain why</p>	<p>open answer</p>
<p>4.47 (8.7) Which output would you expect from a biodiversity digital model or tool?</p> <p>(Multiple answers possible)</p>	<p>An overall score for total biodiversity on the farm/field, A score for several specific species groups (e.g. birds, mammals, insects, plants, ...), A proxy for biodiversity effects generated by implementing agroforestry elements, Proposed actions (e.g. hedgerow planting) to increase biodiversity on the farm/field,</p>
<p>4.48 (8.8) If you chose 'A score for several specific species groups (e.g. birds, mammals, insects, plants, ...) biodiversity' in the previous question: which groups do you prefer and why?</p> <p>(Add as many answers as you desire on separate lines.)</p>	<p>open answer</p>
<p>4.49 (8.9) What do you think is the optimal spatial scale for a biodiversity digital model or tool? (Multiple answers possible)</p>	<p>Plot/field level (one field within a farm), Farm level (all the land managed within a farm (e.g. also includes small forests patches)), Landscape level (beyond, a large area with all its streams, woodlands, pastures, cropland, villages ...),</p>
<p>4.50F (8.10F) (Only respond if you are a farmer or advisor)</p> <p>What amount of time per year are you willing to invest in biodiversity assessment?</p> <p>(activities such as filling in data, using a tool or model, etc.)</p> <p>(hours) : (minutes)</p>	<p>time</p>
<p>4.51.F (8.11F) (Only respond if you are a farmer or advisor)</p> <p>What should be an input of the biodiversity assessment digital model or tool? [The current management of the farm/field.]</p>	<p>Yes, No, Maybe</p>

<p>4.51.F (8.11F) (Only respond if you are a farmer or advisor)</p> <p>What should be an input of the biodiversity assessment digital model or tool? [The amount of trees (and tree species) on the farm/field.]</p>	<p>Yes, No, Maybe</p>
<p>4.51.F (8.11F) (Only respond if you are a farmer or advisor)</p> <p>What should be an input of the biodiversity assessment digital model or tool? [Some easy to record and charismatic species (e.g. birds).]</p>	<p>Yes, No, Maybe</p>
<p>4.52.F (8.12F) (Only respond if you are a farmer or advisor)</p> <p>What should be an input of the biodiversity assessment digital model or tool?</p> <p>Other ideas?</p> <p>(Add as many answers as you desire on separate lines.)</p>	<p>open answer</p>
<p>4.53 (8.13) How should the digital model or tool be constructed?</p>	<p>Based only on publicly available maps, Based on a checklist of the current management and status of the farm/field, A mixed approach,</p>
<p>4.54 (8.14) What kind of digital model or tool would you like to use?</p> <p>(Multiple answers possible)</p>	<p>Website on the internet, Freely available computer program, QGIS/arcGIS-tool (software to handle maps), Excel spreadsheet, R program (software for data-analysis),</p>
<p>4.55 (8.15) What species groups do you think are relevant or are you interested in to validate the digital model or tool?</p> <p>(Multiple answers possible)</p>	<p>Plants, Birds, Bats, Other mammals, Butterflies, Moths, Pollinators (e.g. bees, bumblebees, ...), Spiders, Other arthropods, Amphibians & reptiles, Mushrooms, Earthworms, Soil fauna (e.g. woodlice, millipedes, nematodes, ...),</p>
<p>Would you like to respond to some questions about social and psychological factors influencing the use of digital tools in agroforestry?</p> <p>This will take 9-12 minutes</p> <p>If you're not a farmer, please select "no" and move forward in the survey completion</p>	<p>Yes, I am a farmer and I would like to respond, No, I am not interested, No, I am not a farmer</p>

<p>5.1 (3.1) With the following question, we would like to understand more precisely where your farm is right now with digital development. Please tick the answer that best applies to you at this moment.</p>	<p>The term digitalization in agroforestry means nothing to me., I have already learned about the existence of digital technologies in agroforestry. However, I don't know the details yet and I don't feel the need for more detailed information, I am aware of the existence of digital technologies in agroforestry and am already seeking information, I am familiar with digital tools in agroforestry and have evaluated their advantages and disadvantages for me and decided to use a technology or not to use it., I use digital tools in agroforestry on a limited basis and am looking for more information on this., I use digital tools in agroforestry regularly., I prefer not to say,</p>
<p>5.2 (3.2) How do you assess your overall financial situation?</p>	<p>Linear scale 1-5</p>
<p>5.3 (3.3) Connectivity questions [The internet connection on my agroforestry farm is sufficient for the use of digital technologies.]</p>	<p>I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.3 (3.3) Connectivity questions [Mobile reception on my agroforestry farm is sufficient for the use of digital technologies.]</p>	<p>I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.4 (3.4) What is your attitude towards the phenomenon of digitalization in agriculture? [---]</p>	<p>very negative, negative, neutral, positive, very positive, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.5 (3.5) How do you view the phenomenon of digitalization in agroforestry? [--]</p>	<p>very negative, negative, neutral, positive, very positive, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [1. I am rather reserved]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [2. I trust others easily, believe in the good in people.]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [3. I am comfortable, tend to be lazy.]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [4. I am relaxed, do not let stress upset me.]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [5. I have little artistic interest.]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [6. I get out of myself, am sociable.]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [7. I tend to criticize others.]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>

5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [8. I complete tasks thoroughly.]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [9. I get nervous and insecure easily.]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.6 (3.7) How do the following statements apply to you? (please select one answer per line) [10. I have an active imagination, am imaginative.]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.7 (3.8) How important are the following statements to you? (please select one answer per line) [1. To be my own boss is to me....]	Totally unimportant, Rather unimportant, Neutral, Rather important, Totally important, I prefer not to say
5.7 (3.8) How important are the following statements to you? (please select one answer per line) [2. To be able to repair and maintain my machines myself is to me ...]	Totally unimportant, Rather unimportant, Neutral, Rather important, Totally important, I prefer not to say
5.7 (3.8) How important are the following statements to you? (please select one answer per line) [3. To be independent of experts is to me ...]	Totally unimportant, Rather unimportant, Neutral, Rather important, Totally important, I prefer not to say
5.8 (3.9) What is your overall workload? [What is your overall workload?]	Too little, adequate, Too much, I prefer not to say
5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [1. I like to occupy myself in greater detail with digital services.]	Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [2. I like testing the functions of new digital services.]	Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [3. I predominantly deal with digital services because I have to.]	Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [4. When I have a new digital service in front of me, I try it out intensively.]	Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say

<p>5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [5. I enjoy spending time becoming acquainted with a new digital service. .]</p>	<p>Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [6. It is enough for me that a digital service works; I don't care how or why.]</p>	<p>Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [7. I try to understand how a digital service exactly works.]</p>	<p>Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [8. It is enough for me to know the basic functions of a digital service.]</p>	<p>Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.9 (3.10) The following is about your interaction with technology in general. By "digital services" we mean apps and other software applications as well as cell phones, computers, navigation systems (please select one answer per line). [9. I try to make full use of the capabilities of a digital service.]</p>	<p>Do not agree at all, Do not agree, Rather agree, Agree, Totally agree, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [1. I intend to use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm in the next 5 years.]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [3. I have a very strong intention to use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm in the next 5 years]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>
<p>5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [4. Using digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm reduces the amount of inputs (e.g., fertilizers) into the farm]</p>	<p>Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say</p>

5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [5. Using digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm provides more economic benefits compared to not using it]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [6. I need to use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm to maximize production]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [7. I need to use digital models and tools in agroforestry to save working time]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [8. Most people who are important to me think I should use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [9. Farm consultants think I should use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [10. Other farmers whom I regularly interact with would approve that I should use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [11. I feel under social pressure from fellow farmers to use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [12. I feel that I have sufficient knowledge to use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [13. I have all the conditions (e.g. internet, finance, fit of the technology) I need to use digital models and tools in agroforestry on my farm]	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say
5.10 (3.11) Some questions regarding your intention to use digital services in agroforestry systems: [14. I am confident that I can overcome barriers that prevent me from using digital models	Does not apply at all, Does not apply, Neutral, Applies, Applies completely, I prefer not to say

and tools in agroforestry on my farm in the next 5 years.]	
5.11 (3.12) Do you collect farm data digitally on your farm or use apps or software to manage your farm (e.g. pasture/vegetation mapping, yield mapping, soil mapping and data on feeding of individual animals or herds)?	Yes, No, I prefer not to say,
5.12 (3.13) A question about your knowledge of data use: [Does your contract with the service provider/vendor cover data collection for the tools (such as machines, software and apps) used to collect data on the farm?]	I know nothing about it at all, I know nothing about it, Neutral, I know something about it, I know very much about it, I prefer not to say
5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [1. I agree that service/technology providers such as John Deere or weather station providers have direct access to my operational data about the services they provide to me.]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [2. I agree that service providers / technology providers have direct access to all customer data, including my data, and use that data to generate profit for themselves]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [3. I agree to pay more for the service or technology in exchange for retaining the rights over my operational data myself.]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [4. I agree to the service providers / technology vendors using my operational data in exchange for me paying less for the service or technology.]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [5. I agree to share farm data, such as fertilizer and pesticide use, with technology providers and service providers.]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [6. I agree to share farm data, such as fertilizer and pesticide application, with authorities (state, EU, regional government).]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [7. I agree to share production data with technology providers and service providers.]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say

5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [8. I agree to share production data with authorities (state, EU, regional government).]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree, I prefer not to say
5.13 (3.14) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (please select one answer per line) [9. I agree that my data are stored centrally on a server.]	I do not agree at all, I do not agree, I rather agree, I agree, I totally agree
5.14 (3.15) Some questions regarding your confidence towards data security? (please select one answer per line) [1. If the service / technology providers have direct access to my data, how much confidence do I have that they will maintain the privacy of my operational data?]	No trust at all, Rather no trust, Neutral, Rather high trust, High trust, I prefer not to say
5.14 (3.15) Some questions regarding your confidence towards data security? (please select one answer per line) [2. If the service / technology providers have direct access to my data, how much confidence do I have that they will not share the data with third parties?]	No trust at all, Rather no trust, Neutral, Rather high trust, High trust, I prefer not to say
6.1 (9.1) Would you like to be regularly updated on DigitAF and project-related activities?	Yes, No,
6.2 (9.2) If you want to stay updated, how do you prefer to receive the information?	Newsletter, Website, Social media, In-person meetings, Online meetings,
6.3 (9.3) Through which knowledge sharing format would you like to learn more?	Reports/Publications, Follow-up articles (both at project and industry level), Events/Webinars/Conferences,
6.4 (9.4) How do you currently stay up-to-date on latest researches and developments? [I talk with other experts]	Never, Rarely, Occasionally, Frequently, Always, I prefer not to say
6.4 (9.4) How do you currently stay up-to-date on latest researches and developments? [I read scientific papers]	Never, Rarely, Occasionally, Frequently, Always, I prefer not to say
6.4 (9.4) How do you currently stay up-to-date on latest researches and developments? [I follow other projects]	Never, Rarely, Occasionally, Frequently, Always, I prefer not to say
6.4 (9.4) How do you currently stay up-to-date on latest researches and developments? [I experiment on my own farm]	Never, Rarely, Occasionally, Frequently, Always, I prefer not to say
6.4 (9.4) How do you currently stay up-to-date on latest researches and developments? [I read material on the internet/watch you tube tutorials/videos]	Never, Rarely, Occasionally, Frequently, Always, I prefer not to say
6.4 (9.4) How do you currently stay up-to-date on latest researches and developments? [Other]	Never, Rarely, Occasionally, Frequently, Always, I prefer not to say
6.5 (9.5) What is the purpose of the DigitAF's network closest to your wish?	To connect with other professionals and exchange ideas, tools and knowledge, To stay up-to-date on agroforestry, To access research papers, reports and best practices, To be part of a wider team, I prefer not to say,

6.7 (10.1) Please type a question you'd like to ask about agroforestry or digital tools.

open answer

You can add as many questions as you like!

This will help us
1) focus our research on the questions that are important to you and
2) tailor our communication strategy to answer frequently asked questions.